

ISic1026

I.Sicily inscription 1026

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication; funerary
(?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140505

1. Ἀφροδίτα [ι — —]

2.

Edition: PHI175423

1. Ἀφροδίτα[ι — — —].

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492654

EDCS 39102180

PHI 140505

PHI 175423

Bibliography

- Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0206 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
- Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum*. Berlin. At 3.5433
- Judica, G. 1819. *Le antichità di Acre*. Messina. At tav.XIII.4 and 112
- Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. *Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi*. In Bernabò Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.13
- Bernabò Brea, L. 1956. *Akrai*. Catania. At 139 no.18
- Consani, C. 1996. *Koinai et Koiné dans la documentation épigraphique de l'Italie méridionale*. In Brixhe, C.(eds.), *La Koié grecque antique. II. La concurrence*. pp. 113-132. At 120

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1026. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385355>